

Selective Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with Sodium Pentamethylene Dithiocarbamate

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The use of derivatives of diethyl dithiocarbamates¹ in the extraction of palladium in strong acidic medium is found to be inadequate because of the decomposition of these derivatives at lower pH. To overcome this difficulty John and William² suggested cyclopentamethylene, diphenyl and dibenzyl dithiocarbamates as ligands for strong acidic medium and extracted the complex into chloroform. The dibenzyl derivative was found to react more favourably among the three in the presence of diverse ions, but the time required for the formation of the complex to minimise the interferences is about 30 min.

In view of the time-taking processes and decomposition difficulties in acid medium, we have developed a simple method in which piperidine dithiocarbamate (Pipdte) forms complexes with palladium(II) almost immediately and using a medium close to neutral pH. This reagent (Pipdte) has been found to be sensitive for the determination of number of metal ions³.

Results and Discussion

It is found that neither the reagent nor simple metal ion has any absorbance at 300 nm. It is noticed that $5.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ aqueous solution of Pipdte and 1 ml of $0.2 M$ $MgSO_4$ as salting out agent cause quantitative extraction within 1–2 min of shaking in single step.

In order to establish an effective extraction of Pd (Pipdte)₂ complex at pH 6.5 various solvents like n-butanol, isoamyl alcohol, MIBK, chloroform, 1,4-dioxan, carbon tetrachloride, nitrobenzene, benzene and hexane were tried and chloroform was found to be most effective. The complex is also found to be appreciably stable in this solvent for 24 h. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range $0.5-2.0 \mu g ml^{-1}$ of Pd. The molar absorptivity of the complex is $1.106 \times 10^4 dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ and

the Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0096 \mu g cm^{-2}$. The composition of the complex found by Job's method of continuous variation, molar-ratio method and Asmus method is found to be 1 : 1.

The instability constant of the complex calculated by Edmonds-Birnbaum's method (3.498×10^{-6}) and that by Asmus method (3.173×10^{-6}) corroborate each other.

Effect of foreign ions : Cations like Ag^I , Sn^{II} , Sr^{II} , U^{VI} and Zn^{II} do not interfere even when present upto $1000 \mu g$. Tungsten can be tolerated upto $500 \mu g$ excess. The interference due to Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} and Mo^{VI} can be masked with sodium potassium tartrate, and Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with EDTA. Copper interferes but traces can be masked with EDTA. Among the various anions studied, ascorbic acid is found to interfere severely.

From the results it may be inferred that palladium(II) can be satisfactorily determined by the extractive spectrophotometric technique with (Pipdte). The method is simple and less time-consuming. It is also advantageous over other methods in terms of sensitivity as the detection limit of Pd^{II} is $0.5 \mu g ml^{-1}$.

Experimental

The Na (Pipdte) was prepared by the reported method³. Stock solution of the reagent was prepared in double-distilled water. Standard palladium(II) solution was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (Johnson and Mathey) in $2.0 M$ HCl and standardised⁴. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their chlorides, sulphates or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. Sodium acetate ($0.2 M$) and acetic acid ($0.2 M$) solutions were mixed in suitable ratios for the pH range 3.0–7.0, and ammonium chloride ($0.2 M$) and ammonium hydroxide solutions for the pH range

7.0–10.0. Chloroform was distilled before use. All other chemicals used were A.R. grade unless otherwise mentioned. Magnesium sulphate was used as a salting-out agent. Absorbance measurements are made using a Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer and pH adjustments are made on an Elico LI-10 pH meter.

An aliquot of palladium(II) solution, 0.2 M acetate buffer (2.0 ml), 5.5×10^{-5} Na (Pipdte) solution (1.0 ml), salting out agent (1.0 ml) and distilled water (6.0 ml) were mixed to keep the volume 10 ml. The solution was shaken with chloroform (5.0 ml) for 1 min. After equilibration the organic layer was separated and the absorbance was measured at 300 nm against reagent blank.

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